

Part 1: General/background information

Q1.1: What is your role in the company? (e.g., developer, tech lead, project manager, product manager.)

Q1.2: In which team/project are you currently working?

- Team 1
- Team 2
- Team 3

Q1.3: For how long have you been working in the company?

Q1.4: What is your overall work experience in industry, including the current and previous job?

Q1.5: Have you been involved in the development of reusable assets? Please select as many as applicable to you. If it is something other than the options presented below, you can specify that in option "Other".

- Code (e.g., npm packages, reusable microservices)
- Requirements (e.g., use cases, features)
- Test cases
- No, I have not participated in the development of any reusable assets.
- Other

Q1.6: Have you been involved in the maintenance of reusable assets? Please select as many as applicable to you. If it is something other than the options presented below, you can specify that in option "Other".

- Code (e.g., npm packages, reusable microservices)
- Requirements (e.g., use cases, features)
- Test cases
- No, I have not participated in the development of any reusable assets.
- Other

Q1.7: Have you been consuming the reusable assets in your work? Please select as many as applicable to you. If it is something other than the options presented below, you can specify that in option "Other".

- Code (e.g., npm packages, reusable microservices)
- Requirements (e.g., use cases, features)
- Test cases
- No, I have not participated in the development of any reusable assets.
- Other

Part 2: Questions related to reuse practices/assets

In Part 2, we will ask questions related to the development, maintenance, ownership and planning of the reusable assets. The questions are divided into the following categories: assets, process, collaboration, measurement, rewards, culture.

In this part, the questions are asked twice:

1. For the CURRENT STATUS, and
2. For the DESIRED STATUS

2.1 Category - Assets (code assets) Category - Assets (code assets)

Questions about code repository (ALL CODE IN GENERAL)

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: The teams have their own code repositories, which are not shared with others.
- Status 2: The teams have their own code repositories, and they share it with certain stakeholders outside their team.
- Status 3: The teams have centralized code repositories and anyone in the organization can ask for access.
- Status 4: Teams have centralized code repositories, which, by default, are accessible to everyone in the organization.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: The teams have their own code repositories, which are not shared with others.
- Status 2: The teams have their own code repositories and they share it with certain stakeholders outside their team.
- Status 3: The teams have centralized code repositories and anyone in the organization can ask for access.
- Status 4: Teams have centralized code repositories, which, by default, are accessible to everyone in the organization.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.2 Category - Assets (code assets)

Questions about code repository (ONLY reusable assets like common NPM packages, microservices)

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: The code repository for the reusable assets is accessible only to the team that developed it.
- Status 2: The code repository for the reusable assets is accessible to the team that developed it and they share it only with certain stakeholders outside their team (e.g., on request).
- Status 3: There is a centralized code repository for reusable assets and anyone in the organization can request access to it.
- Status 4: There is a centralized code repository for reusable assets and by default is accessible to everyone in the organization.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The code repository for the reusable assets is accessible only to the team that developed it.

Status 2: The code repository for the reusable assets is accessible to the team that developed it and they share it only with certain stakeholders outside their team (e.g., on request).

Status 3: There is a centralized code repository for reusable assets and anyone in the organization can request access to it.

Status 4: There is a centralized code repository for reusable assets and by default is accessible to everyone in the organization.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.3 Category - Assets (code assets)

Questions about documentation of the reusable code assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: There is no agreed upon policy /structure for the documentation (e.g., readme files) of the reusable assets. Readme files rarely exist for some reusable assets.

Status 2: Some individuals and teams produce documentation for the reusable assets they develop, but as such there is no policy for doing it consistently. Readme files may exist, but lack enough information for understanding/reuse.

Status 3: There is a policy/structure for the documentation of the reusable assets, but it is not consistent across all teams in the organization.

Status 4: There is a consistent organization wide policy/structure for documenting the reusable assets (e.g., consistent structure for writing non-trivial readme files).

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: There is no agreed upon policy /structure for the documentation (e.g., readme files) of the reusable assets. Readme files rarely exist for some reusable assets.

Status 2: Some individuals and teams produce documentation for the reusable assets they develop, but as such there is no policy for doing it consistently. Readme files may exist, but lack enough information for understanding/reuse.

Status 3: There is a policy/structure for the documentation of the reusable assets, but it is not consistent across all teams in the organization.

Status 4: There is a consistent organization wide policy/structure for documenting the reusable assets (e.g., consistent structure for writing non-trivial readme files).

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.4 Category - Assets (code assets)

Questions about discoverability of reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Individuals and teams discover reusable assets due to their personal knowledge (e.g., after talking to a colleague), as such there is no space (e.g., a portal like a marketplace) for sharing the information about reusable assets.

Status 2: The information about the reusable assets exists (in emails, chat, other forums), but is not consolidated in one place. It is possible to find the relevant reusable assets, but it takes some effort.

Status 3: There is a shared space (e.g., a portal like a marketplace), accessible to everyone in the organization. However, it lacks good search facility and only stores basic information and links (e.g., to relevant repository) about the complete reusable assets.

Status 4: There is a shared space, accessible to everyone in the organization, which has information about all the reusable assets (both existing and planned reusable assets). The shared space has good search facility and it's known to everyone.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Individuals and teams discover reusable assets due to their personal knowledge (e.g., after talking to a colleague), as such there is no space (e.g., a portal like a marketplace) for sharing the information about reusable assets.

Status 2: The information about the reusable assets exists (in emails, chat, other forums), but is not consolidated in one place. It is possible to find the relevant reusable assets, but it takes some effort.

Status 3: There is a shared space (e.g., a portal like a marketplace), accessible to everyone in the organization. However, it lacks good search facility and only stores basic information and links (e.g., to relevant repository) about the complete reusable assets.

Status 4: There is a shared space, accessible to everyone in the organization, which has information about all the reusable assets (both existing and planned reusable assets). The shared space has good search facility and it's known to everyone.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.5 Category - Assets (code assets)

Questions about support for contributing/maintaining the code of the reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: It is not possible to pull/build and test the code locally without the active help of the individual/team that developed it.

Status 2: Pulling the code and setting it up to run locally is not well defined and often requires reaching out to the team for help, which developed the code.

Status 3: External developers can build and test the code locally with minimum help from the team that developed it.

Status 4: External developers can pull, build and test the code independently without active help from the individual/team that developed the code.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: It is not possible to pull/build and test the code locally without the active help of the individual/team that developed it.

Status 2: Pulling the code and setting it up to run locally is not well defined and often requires reaching out to the team for help, which developed the code.

Status 3: External developers can build and test the code locally with minimum help from the team that developed it.

Status 4: External developers can pull, build and test the code independently without active help from the individual/team that developed the code.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.6 Category - Assets (Plans/roadmaps)

Questions about plans/roadmaps for all projects

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Teams do not regularly disclose their plans to relevant stakeholders (both in and out of their own project/product unit). No formal actions exists at the organization.

Status 2: Teams give visibility to their plans and roadmaps only to specific stakeholders, before they are started.

Status 3: There are already shared project/product plans and roadmaps to the entire organization but this is not standardized across the organization and not all of the teams/projects provide this information.

Status 4: The project/product plans and roadmaps are shared by default and there is a standard process and homogeneous way to do this across the organization for each project.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Teams do not regularly disclose their plans to relevant stakeholders (both in and out of their own project/product unit). No formal actions exists at the organization.

Status 2: Teams give visibility to their plans and roadmaps only to specific stakeholders, before they are started.

Status 3: There are already shared project/product plans and roadmaps to the entire organization but this is not standardized across the organization and not all of the teams/projects provide this information.

Status 4: The project/product plans and roadmaps are shared by default and there is a standard process and homogeneous way to do this across the organization for each project.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.7 Category - Assets (Plans/roadmaps)

Questions about plans/roadmaps for reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: As such there is no plan/roadmap for developing the reusable assets. The teams do not plan for it, but when they notice an opportunity/need for developing a reusable asset within the team, they just do that on their own.

Status 2: Some teams at the local level have their own plan/roadmap to develop reusable assets, but these plans are not shared outside the teams.

Status 3: Some teams at the local level prepare and align their plans/roadmaps to develop reusable assets, and these plans are shared with certain stakeholders outside the team as well (on demand/need basis).

Status 4: There is a standard process/practice at the organization level for all teams to prepare and share their plans/roadmaps for developing reusable assets. The roadmaps for reusable assets are open to everyone for their feedback and participation (e.g., if other teams or individuals also want to contribute).

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: As such there is no plan/roadmap for developing the reusable assets. The teams do not plan for it, but when they notice an opportunity/need for developing a reusable asset within the team, they just do that on their own.

Status 2: Some teams at the local level have their own plan/roadmap to develop reusable assets, but these plans are not shared outside the teams.

Status 3: Some teams at the local level prepare and align their plans/roadmaps to develop reusable assets, and these plans are shared with certain stakeholders outside the team as well (on demand/need basis).

Status 4: There is a standard process/practice at the organization level for all teams to prepare and share their plans/roadmaps for developing reusable assets. The roadmaps for reusable assets are open to everyone for their feedback and participation (e.g., if other teams or individuals also want to contribute).

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.8 Category - Assets (Plans/roadmaps)

Questions about sprint/release planning for reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The teams' backlogs (sprint/release) do not include tasks related to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. When there is a need to do some work on reusable asset, it may either require overtime from some team members or the other planned tasks gets delayed.

Status 2: Development/maintenance of reusable assets is not planned, but when a need arises to work on the reusable assets, sprint/release plan is adjusted to create capacity for such a work.

Status 3: Development/maintenance of reusable assets is planned by some project managers in the sprint/release backlogs. But as such there is no consistent policy across the organization for allocating some capacity (in sprint/release plans) for development/maintenance reusable assets.

Status 4: There is a consistent policy/approach for addressing the development/maintenance of reusable assets by all project managers in their sprint/release backlogs/plans.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The teams' backlogs (sprint/release) do not include tasks related to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. When there is a need to do some work on reusable asset, it may either require overtime from some team members or the other planned tasks gets delayed.

- Status 2: Development/maintenance of reusable assets is not planned, but when a need arises to work on the reusable assets, sprint/release plan is adjusted to create capacity for such a work.
- Status 3: Development/maintenance of reusable assets is planned by some project managers in the sprint/release backlogs. But as such there is no consistent policy across the organization for allocating some capacity (in sprint/release plans) for development/maintenance reusable assets.
- Status 4: There is a consistent policy/approach for addressing the development/maintenance of reusable assets by all project managers in their sprint/release backlogs/plans.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.9 Category – Other assets

Questions about reusable test cases

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: There is no explicit initiative/effort to practice reuse of test cases in the organization.
- Status 2: Some individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases on their own. In some instances, reuse of test cases happens, but within the same team/project.
- Status 3: In some teams/projects, there is an explicit focus on test case reuse. Some individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases. The reusable cases are available to everyone within the same team/project, and on demand to anyone in the organization.
- Status 4: There is a standard policy at the organization level to focus on the test case reuse. Individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases, which are available by default to everyone in the organization. Test case reuse happens both within and across teams/projects.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: There is no explicit initiative/effort to practice reuse of test cases in the organization.
- Status 2: Some individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases on their own. In some instances, reuse of test cases happens, but within the same team/project.
- Status 3: In some teams/projects, there is an explicit focus on test case reuse. Some individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases. The reusable cases are available to everyone within the same team/project, and on demand to anyone in the organization.
- Status 4: There is a standard policy at the organization level to focus on the test case reuse. Individuals and teams manage and archive potentially reusable test cases, which are available by default to everyone in the organization. Test case reuse happens both within and across teams/projects.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.10 Category – Other assets

Questions about traceability for reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: Traceability links among the requirements, code and test cases for the reusable assets do not exist in most cases.

- Status 2: The traceability link among different assets exists within the team. However, there is no consistent policy/approach of doing it.
- Status 3: Some teams have a policy/structure for maintaining the traceability links among the requirements, code and test cases of the reusable assets. But it is not consistent across all teams in the organization.
- Status 4: There is an organization wide consistent policy for maintaining the traceability links among requirements, code and test cases of the reusable assets.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: Traceability links among the requirements, code and test cases for the reusable assets do not exist in most cases.
- Status 2: The traceability link among different assets exists within the team. However, there is no consistent policy/approach of doing it.
- Status 3: Some teams have a policy/structure for maintaining the traceability links among the requirements, code and test cases of the reusable assets. But it is not consistent across all teams in the organization.
- Status 4: There is an organization wide consistent policy for maintaining the traceability links among requirements, code and test cases of the reusable assets.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.11 Category – Other assets

Questions about other knowledge

Other knowledge could be: decision logs, issue logs, wiki pages about what tools the company use, guidelines about where to find those informations, communication/discussion logs.

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: The teams do not have any knowledge sharing space as such. Most of the knowledge is in the email/chat threads etc.
- Status 2: The teams have their own knowledge space, which is not shared with others.
- Status 3: The teams have their own knowledge space and they share it with certain stakeholders outside (the team). Criteria of the information confidentiality is not clear.
- Status 4: The teams have centralized knowledge space and everyone in the organization can access it. Individuals and teams withhold sensitive data and resources, provide limited details, context and scope. And other members understand why they cannot access certain data or resources.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: The teams do not have any knowledge sharing space as such. Most of the knowledge is in the email/chat threads etc.
- Status 2: The teams have their own knowledge space, which is not shared with others.
- Status 3: The teams have their own knowledge space and they share it with certain stakeholders outside (the team). Criteria of the information confidentiality is not clear.
- Status 4: The teams have centralized knowledge space and everyone in the organization can access it. Individuals and teams withhold sensitive data and resources, provide limited details, context and scope. And other members understand why they cannot access certain data or resources.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.12 Category – Process

Questions about code review process

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Code reviews happen on demand, and are done by internal team members. As such, there is no policy for handling code reviews.

Status 2: Most teams have an internal policy for handling code reviews. Code reviews happen within the same team.

Status 3: Most teams have an internal policy for code reviews where all submissions are reviewed by internal team members. Code reviews by external team members are also happening in some cases on demand.

Status 4: Code review process is universal for all submissions regardless of which team authored the code. Code reviews are performed by both, internal and external team members.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: Code reviews happen on demand, and are done by internal team members. As such, there is no policy for handling code reviews.

Status 2: Most teams have an internal policy for handling code reviews. Code reviews happen within the same team.

Status 3: Most teams have an internal policy for code reviews where all submissions are reviewed by internal team members. Code reviews by external team members are also happening in some cases on demand.

Status 4: Code review process is universal for all submissions regardless of which team authored the code. Code reviews are performed by both, internal and external team members.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.13 Category – Process

Questions about ownership and maintenance of the reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: There is no agreed upon policy for maintenance of the reusable assets. By default, the team that developed the reusable asset is responsible for its maintenance.

Status 2: The updates to the reusable assets are made by the team or individual that notices the deficiency/bug or need for an enhancement. There is no policy on who reviews the code commits of the reusable assets.

Status 3: The updates to the reusable assets are made by the team or individual that notices the deficiency/bug or need for an enhancement. All code commits to the reusable assets are reviewed by team/individual who developed it.

Status 4: The company has a clear policy about the ownership and maintenance of the reusable assets. One or more members of the team that developed the reusable asset act as the guardians. There are also clear guidelines about how the individuals from other teams can contribute to the reusable assets. The guardians review all code commits before accepting them.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: There is no agreed upon policy for maintenance of the reusable assets. By default, the team that developed the reusable asset is responsible for its maintenance.

Status 2: The updates to the reusable assets are made by the team or individual that notices the deficiency/bug or need for an enhancement. There is no policy on who reviews the code commits of the reusable assets.

Status 3: The updates to the reusable assets are made by the team or individual that notices the deficiency/bug or need for an enhancement. All code commits to the reusable assets are reviewed by team/individual who developed it.

Status 4: The company has a clear policy about the ownership and maintenance of the reusable assets. One or more members of the team that developed the reusable asset act as the guardians. There are also clear guidelines about how the individuals from other teams can contribute to the reusable assets. The guardians review all code commits before accepting them.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.14 Category – Process

Questions about Continuous Integration (CI)

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: CI infrastructure and process not in place.

Status 2: Minimal process and infrastructure for CI. Infrastructure for source code management, version control and regular commits exist. No automated testing.

Status 3: Unit tests are automated. Teams have their own CI process using non corporate/standard CI tools.

Status 4: There is a consistent CI process across the organization. Teams use corporate/standard CI tools. Automated builds execute a range of tests and pre-release checks. Integration tests are automated.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: CI infrastructure and process not in place.
- Status 2: Minimal process and infrastructure for CI. Infrastructure for source code management, version control and regular commits exist. No automated testing.
- Status 3: Unit tests are automated. Teams have their own CI process using non corporate/standard CI tools.
- Status 4: There is a consistent CI process across the organization. Teams use corporate/standard CI tools. Automated builds execute a range of tests and pre-release checks. Integration tests are automated.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.15 Category – Collaboration

Questions about communication channels for reusable assets

Example of communication channels: shared wikis, shared space on company's intranet, and teams/slack channels.

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: There are no processes nor established communication channels for discussing reusable assets. Some members of the organization share materials via private channels or discussions.
- Status 2: The organization is in the process of establishing communication channels for discussions on the reusable assets.
- Status 3: The organization has established some communication channels for discussions about reusable assets. Leaders/managers encourage everyone in the organization to share opinions on reuse practice openly. Managers maintain at least one clear and direct channel for organization members to share opinions constructively on reuse practice.
- Status 4: The organization has established internal communication channels for discussions about reusable assets. Leaders/managers encourage everyone in the organization to share opinions on reuse practice openly. Leaders/managers log the reuse problems, discussion results, feedbacks, and solutions.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: There are no processes nor established communication channels for discussing reusable assets. Some members of the organization share materials via private channels or discussions.
- Status 2: The organization is in the process of establishing communication channels for discussions on the reusable assets.
- Status 3: The organization has established some communication channels for discussions about reusable assets. Leaders/managers encourage everyone in the organization to share opinions on reuse practice openly. Managers maintain at least one clear and direct channel for organization members to share opinions constructively on reuse practice.
- Status 4: The organization has established internal communication channels for discussions about reusable assets. Leaders/managers encourage everyone in the organization to share opinions on reuse practice openly. Leaders/managers log the reuse problems, discussion results, feedbacks, and solutions.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.16 Category – Measurement

Questions about measuring/monitoring reuse

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: No measurement plan/goal in place to monitor the reuse practice, and its costs and benefits.

Status 2: Some teams keep track of the reuse rate in their code base and have an ambition to reach a certain reuse level (e.g., 30% of the total code is reuse code).

Status 3: There is a policy/ambition at the organization level to achieve certain reuse rate to reduce the time to market. Teams measure the reuse rate. However, there is no effort to determine the costs and benefits of reuse (e.g., impact on productivity, quality, time to market).

Status 4: There is an organization wide policy about measuring the costs and benefits of development for and with reuse practice. Metrics of measuring reuse costs and benefits are established both on the project and organization level.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: No measurement plan/goal in place to monitor the reuse practice, and its costs and benefits.

Status 2: Some teams keep track of the reuse rate in their code base and have an ambition to reach a certain reuse level (e.g., 30% of the total code is reuse code).

Status 3: There is a policy/ambition at the organization level to achieve certain reuse rate to reduce the time to market. Teams measure the reuse rate. However, there is no effort to determine the costs and benefits of reuse (e.g., impact on productivity, quality, time to market).

Status 4: There is an organization wide policy about measuring the costs and benefits of development for and with reuse practice. Metrics of measuring reuse costs and benefits are established both on the project and organization level.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.17 Category – Rewards

Questions about rewards for contributing to reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The contribution to the development/maintenance of the reusable assets is not rewarded, but is treated as part of the current assignments.

Status 2: There is no policy as such for rewarding contributions to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. Some managers do that occasionally.

Status 3: Some managers have a policy of rewarding and acknowledging those team members that contribute to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. But, as such there is no organization wide consistent practice about it.

Status 4: There is an organization wide consistent policy about rewarding those individuals and teams that contribute to the development/maintenance of the reusable assets.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The contribution to the development/maintenance of the reusable assets is not rewarded, but is treated as part of the current assignments.

Status 2: There is no policy as such for rewarding contributions to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. Some managers do that occasionally.

Status 3: Some managers have a policy of rewarding and acknowledging those team members that contribute to the development/maintenance of reusable assets. But, as such there is no organization wide consistent practice about it.

Status 4: There is an organization wide consistent policy about rewarding those individuals and teams that contribute to the development/maintenance of the reusable assets.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.18 Category – Culture

Questions about attitude about collaboration on reusable assets

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The collaboration (accepting and contributing code commits) on reusable assets is limited within the team that developed the asset.

Status 2: The practice of accepting/making commits for/to reusable assets from outside the team exist, but happens very rarely. Usually inside-the-team commits have less issues than outside-the-team commits.

Status 3: Individuals from multiple teams actively participate in the development and maintenance of reusable assets by code commits, bug fixes etc. The collaboration on/for reusable assets is accepted within the entire organization.

Status 4: Individuals and teams support the idea of collaborative development of reusable assets. Individuals/teams are willing to take/share the role of guardians (responsible for owning/maintaining) for reusable assets developed by other teams.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

Status 1: The collaboration (accepting and contributing code commits) on reusable assets is limited within the team that developed the asset.

Status 2: The practice of accepting/making commits for/to reusable assets from outside the team exist, but happens very rarely. Usually inside-the-team commits have less issues than outside-the-team commits.

Status 3: Individuals from multiple teams actively participate in the development and maintenance of reusable assets by code commits, bug fixes etc. The collaboration on/for reusable assets is accepted within the entire organization.

Status 4: Individuals and teams support the idea of collaborative development of reusable assets. Individuals/teams are willing to take/share the role of guardians (responsible for owning/maintaining) for reusable assets developed by other teams.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.

2.19 Category – Culture

Questions about managers' views on reuse collaboration

What is the CURRENT STATUS in the company? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: Managers view reuse related work and collaboration between multiple teams as an impediment to feature delivery.
- Status 2: Managers support the reuse related collaborative work, but in most cases prioritize feature delivery to customers, rather than investing in developing reusable assets.
- Status 3: Managers of some teams understand the value of reuse and try to balance the focus on instant customer requirements and development of reusable assets.
- Status 4: Managers have the support from the organization to invest in the development of the reusable assets. They actively try to encourage teams to development for and with reuse.

What should be the DESIRED STATUS in your view? Please select one of the following four options.

- Status 1: Managers view reuse related work and collaboration between multiple teams as an impediment to feature delivery.
- Status 2: Managers support the reuse related collaborative work, but in most cases prioritize feature delivery to customers, rather than investing in developing reusable assets.
- Status 3: Managers of some teams understand the value of reuse and try to balance the focus on instant customer requirements and development of reusable assets.
- Status 4: Managers have the support from the organization to invest in the development of the reusable assets. They actively try to encourage teams to development for and with reuse.

If you have any additional comments (e.g., if you cannot select only one option, or if the options are not clear) about the above questions/options, you can add them here.
